

MULTI-AREA ECONOMIC DISPATCH WITH PROHIBITED OPERATING ZONES USING IMPROVED BAT ALGORITHM

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Abstract:

This paper presents application of Improved Bat algorithm for solving Multi-area economic load dispatch problem (MAED) considering tie line constraint, transmission loss, valve point loading effect and prohibited operating zones. Improved bat algorithm is an optimization algorithm motivated by the echolocation behavior of natural bats in finding their foods. Potency of the algorithm is tested on two area system with six generating units and it is compared with artificial bee colony optimization, differential evolution, evolutionary programming and real coded genetic algorithm. The promising results show the quick convergence and effectiveness of the projected technique.

Key Words: Multi-Area Economic Dispatch, Prohibited Operating Zones, Valve Point Loading Effect, Tie Line Constraint & Improved Bat Algorithm

1. Introduction:

Economic dispatch [1] problem is one of the vital optimization problems in the industrial operation of power systems. The primary objective of the ED problem is to resolve the excellent schedule of online generating units so as to meet the power demand at least possible operating cost under various systems and operating constraints. Generally, in power system the generators are divided into many generation areas and they interconnected by using tie-lines. Multi-area economic dispatch (MAED) is an expansion of economic dispatch. MAED determines the generation level and trade of power between areas such that total fuel cost in all areas is curtailed while satisfying power balance constraints, generating limits constraints and tie-line capacity constraints.

Shoult et al [2] included power transfer limits between areas for solving the economic dispatch problem. This study gives a complete formulation of multi-area generation scheduling, and an idea for multi-area studies. Romano et al. [3] Solved constrained economic dispatch of multi-area systems using the Danzig-Wolfe decomposition principle which reduces the complexity of the problem by separating it into several sub-problems. A.L.Desell et al. [4] Applied a linear programming to transmission constrained generation production cost analysis in power system planning for a large electrical network. Ouyang and Shahidehpour [5] proposed heuristic multi-area unit commitment with economic dispatch with an inclusion of simple and effective tie-line constraint checking. Wang et al.[6] Proposed a decomposition approach for the multi-area generation scheduling with tie-line constraints having non-linear characteristics using expert systems.

Dan Streiffert et al. [7] proposed an Incremental Network Flow Programming algorithm for solving the multi-area economic dispatch problem with transmission constraints. Jayabarathi et al. [8] solved multi-area economic dispatch problems with tie line constraints using evolutionary programming technique. Manoharan et al. [9] explored the efficiency and effectiveness of the various evolutionary algorithms such as the Real-coded Genetic Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization, Differential Evolution

and Covariance Matrix Adapted Evolution Strategy on multi-area economic dispatch problems. Prasanna et al. [10] solved the Security Constrained Economic Dispatch in interconnected power system by using Fuzzy logic strategy incorporated with Evolutionary Programming and with Tabu-Search algorithms. Manisha Sharma et al.[11] compared the search capability and convergence behavior of algorithms such as Classical differential evolution (DE) and its various strategies , Classical particle swarm optimization (PSO), An improved PSO with a parameter automation strategy having time varying acceleration coefficients (PSO-TVAC) for solving MAED problems. P. S. Manoharan et al. [12] proposed an Evolutionary Programming with Levenberg-Marquardt Optimization technique to solve multi-area economic dispatch problems with multiple fuel options. M. Zarei et al. [13] proposed a direct search method (DSM) to solve the two-area economic dispatch of the generating units with some equality and inequality constraints with different kind of complex fuel cost function.

Arthur K. Kordon [14] gives realistic guidelines on how to handle the numerous technical, nontechnical issues and for typical real-world applications. James Kennedy and Russell C. Eberhart [15] explained the dynamic behavior of the swarms and their performance under different optimization problem. Sumathi and surekha [16] gives an idea of applying the optimization problem in the environment of Matlab programming. Andries P. Engelbrecht [17] gives a brief introduction about the evolutionary algorithms and swarm intelligence based algorithms and their effect of parameter on applications. Bijaya Ketan Panigrahi and YuhuiShi [18] gives a collection of swarm intelligence applications on various practical real world problem. Bat algorithm (BA) [19-21] is an optimization algorithm based on echolocation characteristics of bats and developed by mimics of 'bats' foraging behavior. The exploration and exploitation mechanism of BA was well suitable for the real world optimization problems.

In this paper, MAED problem with inclusion of prohibited operating zones, transmission loss, valve point effect and tie line constraint has been solved by using the IBA. The proposed IBA approach has been verified by applying it to test system. The performance of the proposed IBA has been compared with differential evolution (DE), evolutionary programming (EP), real coded genetic algorithm (RCGA), and artificial bee colony optimization (ABCO) as per the literature.

2. Problem Formulation:

The main objective of MAED in electrical power system is to reduce the overall production cost of supplying loads to all areas while satisfying power balance constraints, generating limits constraints and tie-line capacity constraints as much as possible [24].

2.1 Multi-Area Economic Dispatch with Quadratic Cost Function Prohibited Operating Zones and Transmission Losses:

The objective of the MAED problem is:-

$$F_t = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} F_{ij}(P_{ij}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} a_{ij} + b_{ij}P_{ij} + c_{ij}P_{ij}^2 \quad (1)$$

where $F_{ij}(P_{ij})$ is the cost function of j th generator in area i and is usually expressed as a quadratic polynomial; a_{ij} , b_{ij} and c_{ij} are the fuel cost coefficients of j th generator in area i ; N is the number of areas, M_i is the number of committed generators in area i ; P_{ij} is the real power output of j th generator in area i . The MAED problem minimizes F_t subject to the following constraints.

2.1.1 Active Power Balance Constraint

$$\sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} P_{ij} = P_{Di} + P_{Li} + \sum_{k,k \neq i} T_{ik} \quad i \in N \quad (2)$$

The transmission loss P_{Li} of area i may be expressed by using B-coefficients as

$$\sum_i^N P_{Li} = \sum_i^N \left(\sum_{l=1}^{M_i} \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} P_{ij} B_{ilj} P_{il} + \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} B_{0ij} P_{ij} + B_{00i} \right) \quad (3)$$

where P_{Di} real power demand of area i ; T_{ik} is the tie line real power transfer from area i to area k . T_{ik} is positive when power flows from area i to area k and T_{ik} is negative when power flows from area k to area i .

2.1.2 Tie Line Capacity Constraints:

The tie line real power transfer T_{ik} from area i to area k should not exceed the tie line transfer capacity for security consideration.

$$-T_{ik}^{\max} \leq T_{ik} \leq T_{ik}^{\max} \quad (4)$$

Where $-T_{ik}^{\max}$ the power flow is limit from area i to area k and $T_{ik}^{\max}$ is the power flow limit from area k to area i .

2.1.3 Real Power Generation Capacity Constraints:

The real power generated by each generator should be within its lower limit $P_{ij}^{\min}$ and upper limit $P_{ij}^{\max}$, so that

$$P_{ij}^{\min} \leq P_{ij} \leq P_{ij}^{\max} \quad i \in N \quad j \in M_j \quad (5)$$

2.1.4 Prohibited Operating Zone:

The prohibited operating zones are the range of power output of a generator where the operation causes undue vibration of the turbine shaft bearing caused by opening or closing of the steam valve. This undue vibration might cause damage to the shaft and bearings. Normally operation is avoided in such regions. The feasible operating zones of unit can be described as :-

The feasible operating zones of unit can be described as follows:-

$$\begin{aligned} P_{ij}^{\min} &\leq P_{ij} \leq P_{ij,1}^l \\ P_{ij,m-1}^u &\leq P_{ij} \leq P_{ij,m}^l; \quad m = 2,3, \dots, n_{ij} \\ P_{ij,n_{ij}}^u &\leq P_{ij} \leq P_{ij}^{\max} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Where m represents the number of prohibited operating zones of j the generator in area i . $P_{ij,m-1}^u$ is the upper limit of $(m - 1)$ th prohibited operating zone of j th generator in area i . $P_{ij,m}^l$ is the lower of m th prohibited operating zone of j the generator in area i . Total number of prohibited operating zone of j th generator in area i is n_{ij} .

2.2. Multi Area Economic Dispatch with Valve Point Loading:

The generator cost function is obtained from a data point taken during “heat run” tests when input and output data are measured as the unit slowly varies through its operating region. Wire drawing effects, which occur as each steam admission valve in a turbine starts to open, produce a rippling effect on the unit curve. To consider the accurate cost curve of each generating unit, the valve point results in as each steam valve starts to open, the ripples like in the cost function addressing valve-point loadings of generating units is accurately represented as

$$\begin{aligned} F_t &= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} F_{ij}(P_{ij}) = \\ &\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{M_i} \{ a_{ij} + b_{ij} P_{ij} + c_{ij} P_{ij}^2 + |d_{ij} \times \sin\{e_{ij} \times (P_{ij}^{\min} - P_{ij})\} \} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

3. Determination of Generation Level of Slack Generator:

M_i committed generators in area i deliver their power output subject to the power balance constraint (2), tie line capacity constraints (4) and the respective generation capacity constraints (5). Assuming the power loading of first $(M_i - 1)$ generators is known, the power level of the M_i th generator (i.e. the slack generator) is given by

$$P_{iM_i} = P_{Di} + P_{Li} + \sum_{k,k \neq i} T_{ik} - \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} P_{ij} \quad (9)$$

The transmission loss P_{Li} is a function of all generator outputs including the slack generator and it is given by

$$P_{Li} = \sum_{l=1}^{M_i-1} \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} P_{ij} B_{ilj} P_{il} + 2P_{iM_i} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} B_{iM_i j} P_{ij} \right) + B_{iM_i M_i} P_{iM_i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} B_{0ij} P_{ij} + B_{0iM_i} P_{iM_i} + B_{00i} \quad (10)$$

Expanding and rearranging, equation (10) becomes

$$B_{iM_i M_i} P_{iM_i}^2 + \left(2 \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} B_{iM_i j} P_{ij} + B_{0iM_i} - 1 \right) P_{iM_i} + \left(P_{Di} + \sum_{k,k \neq i} T_{ik} + \sum_{l=1}^{M_i-1} \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} P_{ij} B_{ilj} P_{il} + \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} B_{0ij} P_{ij} - \sum_{j=1}^{M_i-1} P_{ij} + B_{00i} \right) = 0 \quad (11)$$

The loading of the slack generator (i.e. M_i th) can then be found by solving equation (11) using standard algebraic method.

4. Overview of Bat Algorithm:

BAT algorithm is an optimization algorithm motivated by the echolocation behaviour of natural bats in finding their foods. It is introduced by Yang and is used for solving many real world optimization problems. Each virtual bat in the initial population employs a homologous manner by doing echolocation for updating its position. Bat echolocation is a perceptual system in which a series of loud ultrasound waves are released to produce echoes. These waves are returned with delays and various sound levels which make bats to discover a specific prey as shown in Fig 1. Some guidelines are studied to enhance the structure of BAT algorithm and use the echolocation nature of bats.

- ✓ Each bats identify the distance between the prey and background barriers using echolocation.
- ✓ Bats fly randomly with velocity v_i at position x_i with a fixed frequency f_{min} (or Wavelength λ), varying wavelength λ (or frequency f) and loudness A_0 to search for prey. They can naturally adopt the wavelength (or frequency) of their emitted pulses and adjust the rate of pulse emission $r \in [0, 1]$, depending on the closeness of their prey.
- ✓ Although the loudness of the bats can be modified in many ways, we consider that the loudness varies from a large (positive) A_0 to a minimum value A_{min} according to the problem taken.

Figure 1: Ecolocation behaviour of bats

A. Initialization of Bat Population:

Population initialization of bats randomly in between the lower and the upper boundary can be achieved by the equation.

$$x_{ij} = x_{\min j} + \text{rand}(0,1) * (x_{\max j} - x_{\min j}) \quad (12)$$

Where $i=1, 2, \dots, n, j=1, 2, \dots, d, x_{\min j}$ and $x_{\max j}$ are lower and upper boundaries for dimension j respectively.

B. Update Process of Frequency, Velocity and Solution:

The step size of the solution is controlled with the frequency factor in BA. This frequency factor is generated randomly in between the minimum and maximum frequency $[f_{\min}, f_{\max}]$. Velocity of a solution is proportional to frequency and new solution depends on its new velocity and it is represented as.

$$f_i = f_{\min} + (f_{\max} - f_{\min})\beta \quad (13)$$

$$v_i^t = v_i^{t-1} + (x_i^t - x^*)f_i \quad (14)$$

$$x_i^t = x_i^{t-1} + v_i^t \quad (15)$$

Where $\beta \in [0, 1]$ indicates randomly generated number, x^* represents current global best solutions. For local search part of algorithm (exploitation) one solution is selected among the selected best solutions and random walk is applied.

$$x_{\text{new}} = x_{\text{old}} + \epsilon A^t \quad (16)$$

Where A^t is average loudness of all bats, $\epsilon \in [0, 1]$ is random number and represents direction and intensity of random-walk.

C. Update Process of Loudness and Pulse Emission Rate:

As iteration increases, the loudness and pulse emission must be updated because when the bat gets closer to its prey then their loudness A usually decreases and pulse emission rate also increases, the updating equation for loudness and pulse emission is given by

$$A_i^{t+1} = \alpha A_i^t \quad (17)$$

$$r_i^{t+1} = r_i^0 [1 - e^{(-\gamma t)}] \quad (18)$$

Where α and γ are constants. r_i^0 and A_i are factors which consist of random values and A_i^0 can typically be $[1, 2]$, while r_i^0 can typically be $[0,1]$.

Pseudo Code of Bat Algorithm:

- ✓ Objective function: $f(x), x=(x_1 \dots x_d)^t$.
- ✓ Initialize bat population x_i and velocity v_i $i=1, 2, \dots, n$.
- ✓ Define pulse frequency f_i at x_i .
- ✓ Initialize pulse rate r_i and loudness A_i .
- ✓ While ($t <$ maximum number of iterations).
- ✓ Generate new solutions by adjusting frequency, and updating velocities and location/solutions.
- ✓ IF ($\text{rand} > r_i$).
- ✓ Select a solution among the best solutions.
- ✓ Generate a local solution around the selected best solution.
- ✓ End if.
- ✓ If ($\text{rand} < A_i$ and $f(x_i) < f(x^*)$).
- ✓ Accept new solutions.
- ✓ Increase r_i , reduce A_i .
- ✓ End if.
- ✓ Ranks the bats and find current best x^* .
- ✓ End while.
- ✓ Display results

5. Improved Bat Algorithm (IBA):

Bat Algorithm is an efficient algorithm at exploitation but has some insufficiency at exploration, thus it can easily get trapped in local minimum on most of the

multimodal test functions. In order to overcome this problem of standard BA, some modifications are made in the update process of frequency to improve exploration and exploitation capability of BA [21].

Normally, in bat algorithm the frequency is randomly generated in between the minimum and maximum value, this frequency will have same effect to all dimensions of solution. In order to adopt the effect of change in dimensions on solutions a dynamic frequency varying concept is assigned in this improved bat algorithm.

$$\text{diff}_j = \sqrt{(x_{ij} - x_j^*)^2} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{range} = \max(\text{diff}) - \min(\text{diff}) \quad (20)$$

$$f_j = f_{\min} + \frac{\sqrt{(\min(\text{diff}) - (\text{diff}_j))^2}}{\text{range}} * (f_{\max} - f_{\min}) \quad (21)$$

The distances between i^{th} solution and global best solution are calculated first then the frequency updating are assigned according to Eq. (21), so the frequency variation is depend on difference in distances as per the Eq. (19).By varying the Frequency the step size of the solutions also varied. Thus, dimensions which are closer to global optimum point do not steer for irrelevant regions. Instead, they locally search around global optimum point. Velocity formulation Eq. (22) must be updated as follows.

$$v_{ij}^t = v_{ij}^{t-1} + (x_{ij}^t - x_{ij}^*)f_j \quad (22)$$

Pseudo Code for Improved Bat Algorithm:

- ✓ Initialize the population of n bats randomly and evaluate the objective function for all bats.
- ✓ Initialize temporary best solution among the solutions.
- ✓ Define frequency as per the Eq. (20-22).
- ✓ Define loudness A_i and the initial velocities v_i ($i= 1, 2, \dots, N$); Set pulse rate r_i .
- ✓ While ($t < \text{maximum number of iterations}$)
- ✓ Evaluate objective function for generating new solutions by varying the frequency and update velocity Eq.(20-22).
- ✓ If ($\text{rand} > r_i$)
- ✓ Select a solution among the best solutions.
- ✓ Generate a local solution around the selected best solution.
- ✓ End if
- ✓ If ($\text{rand} < A_i$ and $f(x_i) < f(x^*)$)
- ✓ Accept new solutions
- ✓ Increase r_i , reduce A_i
- ✓ End if
- ✓ Ranks the bats and find current best x^*
- ✓ End while
- ✓ Display results.

6. Simulation Results and Discussion:

In this work an IBA algorithm is applied to solve the multi-area economic dispatch for three different cases and the potential of the algorithm is compared with the differential evolution (DE), evolutionary programming (EP), artificial bee colony optimization algorithm (ABCO), and real coded genetic algorithm (RGCA). Result obtained from IBA is compared with other algorithms as per Table1, and the convergence characteristic of IBA is shown in Fig 2. The result of comparison between IBA, ABCO, DE, EP and RGCA obtained from Table 1 and the parameter variation of IBA

is shown in Fig 3 shows that improved bat algorithm gives better result. The data for two area system [25] is given in the Table A, and the loss coefficients for the two area generators is given in Appendix A.

Figure 2: Convergence Characteristics of IBA

Table 1
Simulation results

	IBO	ABCO[24]	DE [24]	EP [24]	RCGA[24]
P _{1,1} (MW)	500	500	500	500	500
P _{1,2} (MW)	200	200	200	200	200
P _{1,3} (MW)	149.998	149.9997	150	149.9919	149.6328
P _{2,1} (MW)	204.0006	204.3358	204.3341	206.4493	205.9398
P _{2,2} (MW)	154.9949	154.9954	154.7048	154.8892	155.8322
P _{2,3} (MW)	67.629	67.2915	67.577	65.2717	65.2209
T ₁₂ (MW)	82.7712	82.7728	82.7731	82.7652	82.4135
P _{L1} (MW)	9.4268	9.4269	9.4269	9.4267	9.4193
P _{L2} (MW)	4.1984	4.1955	4.189	4.1754	4.2064
Cost (\$/h)	12255.36	12255.39	12255.42	12255.43	12256.23
CPU time (s)	7.8641	10.9844	11.9219	16.8906	19.6094

The IBA algorithm is employed to solve the economic dispatch of two area system consist of three generators on each area with considering prohibiting zones, transmission loss, generating capacity constraint and tie line limit constraint, the total demand for two area system is 1263MW and it is shared by two areas, area1 demand is 757.8MW (60%), area2 demand is 505.2MW (40%) and the tie-line power flow limit between area 1 and 2 is 100MW.

Figure 3: Parameter Variation of IBA

7. Conclusion:

In this paper, IBA is applied to Multi-area economic load dispatch problems with two area. The results obtained by this method are compared with ABCO, DE, EP and RGCA. The comparison shows that IBA performs better than above mentioned methods. The IBA has superior features including quality of solution, stable convergence characteristics and good computational efficiency for large system. Therefore, this results shows that IBA is a promising technique for solving complicated problems in power system

8. References:

1. Chowdhury BH, Rahman S. A review of recent advances in economic dispatch. *IEEE Trans Power System* 1990; 5(4):1248–59.
2. Shoults RR, Chang SK, Helmick S, Grady WM. A practical approach to unit commitment, economic dispatch and savings allocation for multiple-area pool operation with import/export constraints. *IEEE Trans Power Apparatus System* 1980; 99(2):625–35.
3. Romano R, Quintana VH, Lopez R, Valadez V. Constrained economic dispatch of multi-area systems using the Dantzig–Wolfe decomposition principle. *IEEE Trans Power Apparatus Syst* 1981; 100(4):2127–37.
4. Desell AL, McClelland EC, Tammar K, Van Horne PR. Transmission constrained production cost analysis in power system planning. *IEEE Trans Power Apparatus Syst* 1984; 103(8):2192–8.
5. Ouyang Z, Shahidehpour SM. Heuristic multi-area unit commitment with economic dispatch. *IEE Proc-C* 1991; 138(3):242–52.
6. Wang C, Shahidehpour SM. A decomposition approach to non-linear multi area generation scheduling with tie-line constraints using expert systems. *IEEE Trans Power Syst* 1992; 7(4):1409–18.
7. Streiffert D. Multi-area economic dispatch with tie line constraints. *IEEE Trans Power Syst* 1995; 10(4):1946–51.
8. Jayabarathi T, Sadasivam G, Ramachandran V. Evolutionary programming based multi-area economic dispatch with tie line constraints. *Electr Mach Power Syst* 2000; 28:1165–76.
9. Manoharan PS, Kannan PS, Baskar S, Willjuice Iruthayarajan M. Evolutionary algorithm solution and KKT based optimality verification to multi-area economic dispatch. *Int J Electr Power Energy Syst* 2009; 31(7–8):365–73.
10. Prasanna. T.S, and Somasundaram.P. multi-area security constrained economic dispatch by fuzzy- stochastic algorithms. *Journal of theoretical and applied information technology*. 2005 – 2009.
11. Sharma Manisha, Pandit Manjaree, Srivastava Laxmi. Reserve constrained multi-area economic dispatch employing differential evolution with timevarying mutation. *Int J Electr Power Energy Syst* 2011; 33(3):753–66.
12. Manoharan .P. S., Kannan p. S., Ramanathan. V. A Novel EP Approach for Multi-area Economic Dispatch with Multiple Fuel Options *Turk J Elec Eng & Comp Sci*, Vol.17, No.1, 2009, doi: 10.3906/elk-0705-10.
13. Zarei. M, Roozegar.A, Kazemzadeh.R., and Kauffmann J.M. Two Area Power Systems Economic Dispatch Problem Solving Considering Transmission Capacity Constraints. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Electrical, Computer, Energetic, Electronic and Communication Engineering* Vol: 1, No:9, 2007.
14. Arthur K. Kordon. *Applying Computational Intelligence*. springer 2010.

15. James Kennedy and Russell C. Eberhart. Swarm intelligence. Academic Press 2001.
16. S. sumathi and surekha p. Computational Intelligence Paradigms Theory and Applications using MATLAB. CRC press 2010.
17. Andries P. Engelbrecht. Computational Intelligence an Introduction. John Wiley & Sons 2002.
18. Bijaya Ketan Panigrahi, Yuhui Shi, and Meng-Hiot Lim. Handbook of Swarm Intelligence Concepts, Principles and Applications. Springer 2011.
19. X.-S. Yang, A New Metaheuristic Bat-Inspired Algorithm, in: Nature Inspired Cooperative Strategies for Optimization (NISCO 2010) (Eds. J. R. Gonzalez et al.), Studies in Computational Intelligence, Springer Berlin, 284, Springer, 65-74 (2010).
20. Xin-She Yang, Bat algorithm: literature review and applications, Int. J. Bio-Inspired Computation, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 141-149 (2013). DOI: 10.1504/IJBIC.2013.055093
21. Selim Yilmaz and Ecir U. Kucuksille. Improved Bat Algorithm on Continuous Optimization Problems. Lecture Notes on Software Engineering, Vol. 1, No. 3, August 2013.
22. Walter DC, Sheble GB. Genetic algorithm solution of economic dispatch with valve point loading. IEEE Trans Power Syst 1993; 8:1325-32.
23. Chiang C-L. Improved genetic algorithm for power economic dispatch of units with valve-point effects and multiple fuels. IEEE Trans Power Syst 2005; 20(4):1690-9.
24. Basu.M .Artificial bee colony optimization for multi-area economic dispatch .Electricla power and energy systems 49(2013)181-187.
25. Gaing Z-L. Particle swarm optimization to solving the economic dispatch considering the generator constraints. IEEE Trans Power Syst 2003; 18(3):1187-95.
26. Sinha N, Chakrabarti R, Chattopadhyay PK. Evolutionary programming techniques for economic load dispatch. IEEE Trans Evol Comput 2003; 7(1):83-94.

Table A
 Generator data for two area system

G _{ij}	a _{ij} (\$/h)	b _{ij} (\$/MW h)	c _{ij} (\$/(MW) ² h)	P _{ij} ^{min} (MW)	P _{ij} ^{max} (MW)	Prohibited Zones(MW)
G _{1,1}	550	8.1	0.00028	100	500	[210 240] [350 380]
G _{1,2}	350	7.5	0.00056	50	200	[90 110] [140 160]
G _{1,3}	310	8.1	0.00056	50	150	[80 90] [110 120]
G _{2,1}	240	7.74	0.00324	80	300	[150 170] [210 240]
G _{2,2}	200	8.00	0.00254	50	200	[90 110] [140 150]
G _{2,3}	126	8.06	0.00284	50	120	[75 85] [100 105]

Transmission loss coefficients for two area system

$$B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 17 & 12 & 7 \\ 12 & 14 & 9 \\ 7 & 9 & 31 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-6}$$

$$B_{01} = [-0.3908 \quad -0.1297 \quad 0.7047] \times 10^{-3}$$

$$B_{001} = 0.045$$

$$B_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 24 & -6 & -8 \\ -6 & 129 & -2 \\ -8 & -2 & 150 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-6}$$

$$B_{002} = [0.0591 \quad 0.2161 \quad -0.6635] \times 10^{-3}$$

$$B_{002} = 0.056$$